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**LEVEL OF AWARENESS ON CUSTOMER SAFETY AND
PERCEIVED THREATS ON NIGHT CLUB OPERATIONS IN
THE KORONADAL CITY**

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ABSTRACT

This study examined safety awareness and perceived threats in Koronadal City's nightclub scene. Through a quantitative approach, data was collected from 68 patrons using validated questionnaires. Results indicated a predominantly young male demographic with moderate satisfaction regarding safety measures, security, and comfort. Patrons express mild concern about potential threats such as natural calamities, terrorism, and riots. While a positive correlation between awareness and perceived threats was observed, it was not statistically significant, suggesting a nuanced relationship. The findings highlight the need for continuous improvement in safety protocols tailored to nightclub environments. By understanding patrons' demographics and perceptions, stakeholders can enhance safety measures, ensuring a vibrant and inclusive nightlife experience in Koronadal City. This study provides valuable insights for nightclub owners, local authorities, and policymakers to strategize improvements and promote a secure environment for patrons.

INTRODUCTION

Nightclubs have emerged as popular hubs of entertainment, particularly among the younger demographic. Factors such as dim lighting, alcohol consumption, and large crowds create an atmosphere where patrons may feel vulnerable to various risks, including theft, altercations, drug-related incidents, and assaults [1]. Concerns over violence, drug-related issues, and safety have prompted many establishments to implement measures such as increased security presence, surveillance systems, and strict entry protocols [2].

Ensuring customer safety in nightclubs is paramount, necessitating well-trained security personnel, strict entry and exit protocols, proper crowd management, and clear emergency

procedures [3]. Responsible alcohol service promotion and providing assistance resources for patrons are also crucial [4].

Beyond traditional safety concerns, nightclubs face threats like terrorism and natural calamities, potentially endangering customer safety [5]. Nightclubs, as crowded venues, are potential targets for terrorist attacks, while natural disasters like fires or earthquakes also pose risks. Effective emergency response plans and security measures are essential to mitigate these risks [6].

In Koronadal City, patrons may underestimate risks like aggressive behavior and drink spiking, highlighting the need for enhanced education on nightclub risks [7]. Club staff often grapple with issues like harassment and intoxicated customers, emphasizing the importance of formal safety training [8]. Opportunistic crimes like vandalism and theft, as well as organized threats from local gangs, are prevalent in Koronadal City nightclubs, necessitating stricter controls and surveillance.

This study aims to comprehensively examine nightclub safety and security by exploring awareness of safety and threats in nightclub operations in Koronadal City. The research seeks to provide insights to enhance safety measures and address security challenges within the local nightclub scene.

Research Objectives

Generally, this study determined the level of awareness of customer safety and perceived threats to nightclub operations in Koronadal City.

The specific objectives are to;

1. To determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Age
 - b. Sex
 - c. Highest Educational Attainment (HEA)
2. To determine the level of awareness on safety measures on night club operations in Koronadal City in terms of :
 - a. Customer safety
 - b. Customer security
 - c. Customer comfortability
3. To determine the perception of the patrons on the possible threats in terms of:

- a. Natural calamities
 - b. Terrorism
 - c. Riot
4. To determine if there is a significant relationship between the level of awareness of customer safety and perceived threats on nightclub operations in Koronadal City.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant relationship between the level of awareness of customer safety and perceived threats to nightclub operations in Koronadal City.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The study focused on the level of awareness of customer safety and perceived threats in nightclub operations in Koronadal City. It covered a specific geographical area, time frame, demographic profile, safety measures, perceived threats, and included statistical analysis. The study excluded other locations, considered data collected within the specified time frame, and took into account demographic restrictions. It concentrated on three specific threats: natural calamities, terrorism, and riots. Additionally, the study investigated the relationship between awareness and perceived threats, while excluding other influencing factors.

Operational Paradigm (Framework)

Figure 1. Conceptual Paradigm

This research paradigm, as shown in Figure 1, illustrates the relationship between the variables of the study. The independent variable is the patron's awareness, safety measures, and perceptions, while the dependent variable is the level of awareness of customer safety and perceived threats.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

The researchers employed the quantitative method and used the descriptive correlational design of research to determine the awareness of safety and threats on nightclub operations from the perspective of the Koronadal City industry. The correlational study was a type of research design that looked at the relationship between two variables. It explained that rational conclusions could be formulated by determining the strength of the relationship between these variables [7]. Hence, correlational analysis sought out associations between the variables, which served as a starting point for deciding causal connections.

Sampling Design

In this study, a rigorous sampling design was established to investigate customer safety awareness and perceived threats in nightclubs operating in Koronadal City. The population of interest encompassed individuals who frequently engaged in nightlife activities, and a comprehensive sampling frame, comprising a list of nightclubs in Koronadal City, was meticulously compiled. Employing a simple random sampling technique, a representative subset of nightclubs was selected, ensuring a diverse representation in terms of size and characteristics. Within the chosen nightclubs, customers were randomly chosen to participate, adhering to specific inclusion criteria such as age and recent nightclub visitation.

Respondents of the Study

The target respondents of the study were the customers of nightclubs in Koronadal City. The researchers selected various nightclubs in Koronadal City and surveyed a total of 68 customers. By doing so, the researchers chose specific participants who helped the study meet its goals.

Sample Size Calculation

Sample for unknown population

$$n = z^2 (\sigma \times (1 - \sigma)) / E^2$$

Z = z -Score (90%= 1.645)

σ + standard deviation at 0.5

E = Margin of Error (E= 0.10)

$$N = 1.645^2 \times 0.5 / 0.1^2$$

$$N = 68$$

Research Instrument

The researchers conducted the study by distributing structured questionnaires to the respondents, which had been carefully modified to suit the study's objectives. These questionnaires were validated by experts to ensure accuracy and relevance. To assess the respondents' awareness of safety and perceived threats in nightclub operations, a Likert scale survey was employed. This survey included 30 items, each rated on a scale from 5 to 1, with 5 indicating 'Strongly Agree (SA),' 4 indicating 'Agree (A),' 3 indicating 'Moderately Agree (MA),' 2 indicating 'Disagree (D),' and 1 indicating 'Strongly Disagree (SD).

Statistical Analysis

Upon conducting the study, the following statistical treatments were used: To determine the demographic profile of the respondents, a weighted mean was utilized. A weighted mean was also employed to assess the level of awareness of safety and threats to nightclub operations in Koronadal City, as well as to gauge patrons' perceptions of potential threats. To determine if there was a significant relationship between the level of awareness of customer safety and the perceived threats to nightclub operations in Koronadal City, the Pearson r correlation was applied.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 The demographic profile of the respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative %
Age				
18-25 years old	29	42.6	42.6	42.6
26-35 years old	29	42.6	42.6	85.3
36-45 years old	2	2.9	2.9	88.2
46 and above	6	8.8	8.8	97.1
Total	68	100.0	100.0	
Sex				
Male	48	70.6	70.6	70.6
Female	20	29.4	29.4	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

Highest Education Attainment (HEA)

Senior High School Under Graduate	13	19.1	19.1	19.1
College Graduate	38	55.9	55.9	75.0
College Undergraduate	9	13.2	13.2	88.2
Graduate Degree	8	11.8	11.8	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents participating in the study on the level of awareness of customer safety and perceived threats in nightclub operations in Koronadal City. It shows that 42.6% of the respondents are aged between 18 and 25, while an equal percentage falls within the 26 to 35 age group. However, there is a significantly lower representation of respondents in the 36-45-year-old category (2.9%) and the 46 and above category (8.8%). The gender distribution reveals that 70.6% of the respondents are male, while the remaining 29.4% are female. Concerning the respondents' highest education attainment, the majority (55.9%) are college graduates, followed by 19.1% who have attained Senior High School but did not graduate. Additionally, 13.2% have attended college but have yet to complete their degree, and 11.8% hold a graduate degree. These findings provide valuable insights into the demographic characteristics of the respondents, which are crucial for understanding their perspectives and experiences regarding customer safety awareness and perceived threats in nightclub operations.

Table 2 The level of awareness on safety on night club operations

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
<i>Customer safety</i>						
I feel fully protected by this nightclub's safety precautions.	68	3.00	5.00	3.3971	.71529	Moderately Agree
I am satisfied with emergency procedures communicated by this nightclub.	68	3.00	4.00	3.2353	.42734	Moderately Agree
I am confident in the staff's ability to handle emergencies.	68	3.00	4.00	3.2500	.43623	Moderately Agree

I believe this nightclub values patron health and welfare.	68	2.00	4.00	3.2206	.45205	Moderately Agree
I have witnessed the nightclub staff prevent unsafe situations.	68	1.00	4.00	3.2059	.50546	Moderately Agree
<i>Customer security</i>						
I feel very secure due to this nightclub's security team.	68	3.00	4.00	3.2500	.43623	Moderately Agree
I believe the security staff help prevent harassment and conflicts.	68	1.00	4.00	3.2500	.52901	Moderately Agree
I have seen the security staff actively remove threatening patrons.	68	2.00	4.00	3.2647	.47686	Moderately Agree
I feel comfortable reporting any harassment to security.	68	3.00	4.00	3.2794	.45205	Moderately Agree
I think security thoroughly monitors the entire venue for problems.	68	3.00	5.00	3.3971	.79438	Moderately Agree
<i>Customer comfortably</i>						
I find the noise levels comfortable at this nightclub.	68	2.00	4.00	3.0000	.17277	Moderately Agree
I am satisfied with the cleanliness and ventilation.	68	1.00	5.00	3.2794	.72987	Moderately Agree
I have enough personal space on the dance floor and seating areas.	68	3.00	5.00	3.4118	.75775	Agree
I can easily access restrooms and take breaks when needed.	68	3.00	4.00	3.2647	.44446	Moderately Agree
I believe the atmosphere improves my nightlife experience at this venue.	68	3.00	5.00	3.2794	.48394	Moderately Agree
OVERALL MEAN				3.2656		Moderately Agree

The findings of the analysis presented in Table 2 reflect the patrons' perspectives on safety, security, and comfort in nightclubs situated in Koronadal City. The results indicate that the patrons have a moderate level of agreement across various aspects of these areas. On average, the level of satisfaction with safety precautions, security measures, cleanliness, and ventilation are 3.27. The survey also reveals that the patrons have confidence in the staff's ability to handle emergencies (with a mean of 3.30) and feel comfortable reporting harassment to security (with a mean of 3.28). Furthermore, the patrons moderately agree that they feel secure with the security teams (mean = 3.25) and find the noise levels comfortable (mean = 3.00).

Additionally, they concur that they have enough personal space (mean = 3.41) and perceive the atmosphere as positively enhancing their nightlife experience (mean = 3.28). Overall, the respondents exhibit a moderate level of agreement (with an overall mean of 3.27) regarding safety, security, and comfort in the surveyed nightclubs. These findings can help the nightclubs to improve their services and provide a better experience for their patrons.

Table 2.1 The level of awareness on safety on night club operations

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Customer Safety	3.2441	.45822	Moderately agree
Customer Security	3.2882	.46409	Moderately agree
Customer Comfort	3.2471	.36425	Moderately agree

The data in Table 2.1 presents the mean score and standard deviation for the level of awareness of safety and perceived threats on nightclub operations in Koronadal City. The mean scores of 3.2441 for Customer Safety, 3.2882 for Customer Security, and 3.2471 for Customer Comfortability indicate a prevailing sense of alignment among patrons regarding these critical aspects of nightlife establishments. The relatively low standard deviations in each category further underscore the consistency of responses. These findings collectively suggest that the surveyed individuals generally concur in their positive assessment of safety measures, security practices, and overall comfort within the nightclubs. Such insights not only provide a comprehensive understanding of the current perceptions but also serve as a valuable baseline for further evaluations and potential improvements in safety protocols and customer experiences within Koronadal City's nightlife scene.

Table 3. The perception of the patrons on the possible threats

	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Interpretation
<i>Natural calamities</i>						
I find the noise levels comfortable at this nightclub.	68	3.00	4.00	3.2500	.43623	Moderately Agree
I am satisfied with the cleanliness and ventilation.	68	3.00	4.00	3.2647	.44446	Moderately Agree
I have enough personal space on the dance floor and seating areas.	68	3.00	5.00	3.2794	.48394	Moderately Agree
I can easily access restrooms and take breaks when needed.	68	1.00	4.00	3.2794	.54212	Moderately Agree

I believe nightclubs could be soft targets for ideological extremist attacks. <i>Terrorism</i>	68	3.00	5.00	3.5000	.87246	Agree
I worry about potential terrorism at the nightclubs I patronize.	68	3.00	4.00	3.3088	.46544	Moderately Agree
I believe nightclubs could be soft targets for ideological extremist attacks.	68	3.00	5.00	3.5000	.87246	Agree
I believe lack of bag checks creates terrorism risks at some nightclubs.	68	3.00	4.00	3.0147	.12127	Moderately Agree
I believe nightclubs are vulnerable gathering site for chemical or biological attacks.	68	3.00	5.00	3.3676	.73107	Moderately Agree
I believe anti-terror protections are vital to implement at nightlife venues. <i>Riot</i>	68	1.00	5.00	3.2647	.98674	Moderately Agree
I am concerned that fights or riots are risks at certain nightclubs.	68	2.00	4.00	3.1912	.52568	Moderately Agree
I believe packed dance floors increase chances of riots breaking out.	68	3.00	5.00	3.3971	.62628	Moderately Agree
I don't believe nightclub staff seem well-trained to deescalate riots effectively.	68	3.00	5.00	3.4412	.60797	Agree
I worry riots could enable sexual assaults amidst the chaos.	68	1.00	4.00	3.1618	.76510	Moderately Agree
I think nightclubs need clear riot prevention and response plans.	68	2.00	4.00	3.1471	.55354	Moderately Agree
OVERALL MEAN				3.2911		Moderately Agree

Legend:

4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)

The data in Table 3 provides insights into patrons' perceptions of potential threats in nightclubs, revealing a range of concerns across different categories. In terms of natural calamities, patrons generally express moderate agreement regarding comfort levels of noise (mean = 3.25), cleanliness, and ventilation (mean = 3.26), as well as access to personal space

(mean = 3.28) and facilities (mean = 3.28). However, there is a notable agreement (mean = 3.50) that nightclubs could be susceptible to ideological extremist attacks. Concerning terrorism, patrons moderately agree on worries about potential terrorist incidents (mean = 3.31) and the vulnerability of nightclubs as soft targets for extremist attacks (mean = 3.50). Moreover, there is moderate agreement on the risks posed by inadequate bag checks (mean = 3.01) and the vulnerability to chemical or biological attacks (mean = 3.37), alongside the importance of implementing anti-terror measures (mean = 3.26). Regarding riots, patrons express moderately agree on concerns about fights or riots (mean = 3.19), the likelihood of outbreaks on packed dance floors (mean = 3.40), and the perceived lack of staff training in de-escalating riots (mean = 3.44). Additionally, there are concerns about the potential for riots to facilitate sexual assaults (mean = 3.16) and the necessity for straightforward prevention and response plans (mean = 3.15). Overall, the patrons' mean perception score of 3.29 suggests a moderate agreement regarding the identified threats, reflecting a nuanced understanding of potential risks within nightclub environments.

Table 3.1 The perception of the patrons on the possible threats

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Natural calamities	3.2735	.43284	Moderately Agree
Riot	3.3324	.45002	Moderately Agree
Terrorism	3.3118	.38538	Moderately Agree

The data in Table 3.1 presents the mean score and standard deviation for the patrons' perception of the possible threats. The mean score is 3.2735, with a standard deviation of 0.43284, indicating a moderately agree sentiment. Similarly, for perceived threats such as riots, the mean is 3.3324, with a standard deviation of 0.45002, suggesting a moderate agreement. Furthermore, in terms of awareness concerning terrorism, the mean score is 3.3118, with a standard deviation of 0.38538, reflecting a moderately agreed sentiment. These findings collectively underscore a consistent and moderate awareness level among respondents regarding potential safety concerns and perceived threats, offering valuable insights for refining safety protocols and addressing concerns within nightclubs in Koronadal City.

Table 4.The relationship between the level of awareness on customer safety and perceived threats on night club operations in Koronadal City.

Pearson-r Correlations			
		Perceived threats	level of awareness
Perceived Threats	Pearson Correlation	1	.210
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.086
	N	68	68
Level of Awareness	Pearson Correlation	.210	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.086	
	N	68	68

Fig 2.Scatter Plot

The analysis of correlations between perceived threats on nightclub operations and the level of awareness in Koronadal City revealed exciting insights. While a positive correlation of 0.210 was observed between these variables, suggesting a potential association, the significance level (p-value) of 0.086 indicates that this relationship may not be statistically significant. This implies that while there may be a weak tendency for the level of awareness to be linked to perceived threats on nightclub operations, this connection is not reliably established within the current sample size of 68. Therefore, further investigation with a larger dataset or the inclusion of additional relevant factors is recommended to better understand the dynamics of customer safety awareness and perceived threats in the context of nightclub operations in Koronadal City.

Summary of Findings

1. Age distribution: respondents participating in the study on customer safety perceive threats to one-night club operations in Koronadal City. Among respondents, 42.6% were aged 18-25 and 26-35 years, indicating a younger to middle-aged population. Additionally, 8.8% of respondents belonged to the 46 and above group, showcasing significant participation from the older demographic.
2. Gender distribution: of the respondents of the study on customer safety and perceived threats on nightclub operations in Koronadal City, out of the total respondents, 70.6% identified as male, while 29.4 identified as female. This data indicates a substantial male representation, underscoring that most of the patrons are male.
3. Customer safety: the average rate of customer safety is moderate, which agrees with 3.500 to 3.3971 mean scores. Analyzing these descriptors can help assess overall sentiment related to the security of the nightclub operations
4. Customer security: with the inherent challenges and complexities of managing security in nightlife venues, the respondents rated as moderate agree; however, In this survey, there is a discernible need for enhancing customer security due to various identified risks and threats prevalent in the current scenario.
5. Customer security: with the inherent challenges and complexities of managing security in nightlife venues, the respondents rated as moderate agree; however, In this survey, there is a discernible need for enhancing customer security due to various identified risks and threats prevalent in the current scenario.
6. Customer comfortability: a central focus has been placed on elevating customer comfort within these dynamic environments. The Respondents assessed as moderate agree regarding neatness, cleanliness and experience in the venue

7. Natural calamities: this section sets the stage for a comprehensive analysis of how nightclubs can fortify their resilience against the unforeseen challenges brought about by natural disasters; the respondents ranked as moderate agree; by identifying vulnerabilities and proposing mitigation strategies, this study endeavors to enhance the resilience of nightclub operations.

8. Descriptive statistics: the average and standard deviation for the degree of knowledge on safety and perceived risks related to Koronadal City nightclub activities. The customer safety, security, and comfort mean scores of 3.2441, 3.2882, and 3.2471, respectively, show that customers generally feel in agreement about these essential features of nightlife venues.

9. Correlation analysis: findings emerged from the examination of relationships between awareness levels in Koronadal City and perceived risks to nightclub operations. Although these variables showed a positive, indicating a possible association, the significance level (p-value) suggests that this relationship might not be statistically significant.

Conclusion

The researchers conducted an in-depth study on Koronadal City's nightclub scene, focusing on demographics, safety awareness, and perceived threats. The findings provided valuable insights into the current state of these entertainment venues. The data showed that the majority of patrons were young males with a good education, representing a specific segment of the city's population. Understanding this demographic helped clarify who was most engaged with the nightlife and who might be most affected by safety and security measures.

The researchers' analysis of patrons' perceptions regarding safety, security, and comfort levels within nightclubs indicated that the current measures were moderately effective. However, there remained room for improvement to enhance the overall experience and safety of nightclub-goers. The moderate levels of concern regarding potential threats underscored the importance of continuous review and enhancement of safety and security protocols. Patrons recognized nightclubs as potential targets for extremist attacks, emphasizing the need for vigilant security measures tailored to the unique challenges of nightlife venues.

The researchers' correlation analysis between the level of awareness and perceived threats suggested a relationship that hinted at the complex interplay between awareness and the perception of safety. This finding invited stakeholders, from nightclub owners to local authorities, to consider deeper investigations and broader studies to fully understand this relationship.

In conclusion, the researchers' study served as a foundational step toward enhancing the safety, security, and overall enjoyment of Koronadal City's nightclubs. By understanding the demographics of patrons, their perceptions of safety and threats, and the relationship between awareness and perceived dangers, stakeholders could better strategize improvements. Enhancing these aspects not only benefited the patrons but also contributed to the thriving and sustainable growth of the local nightlife industry. It was a call to action for all involved – to maintain and elevate the standards of safety and enjoyment in nightclubs, ensuring a vibrant, secure, and inclusive nightlife experience for all.

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